

ACTIVATION OF THE VIRTUES OF PATRIOTISM, DILIGENCE, RESPONSIBILITY IN THE HEARTS OF SOCIETY MEMBERS IN PROVIDING INTERNATIONAL HARMONY AND SOLIDARITY IN THE CONDITIONS OF INFORMATION- CULTURAL THREATS

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Abstract: this article analyzes the activation of the qualities of patriotism, hard work, and responsibility in the hearts of members of the society in the context of informational and cultural threats.

Key words: information, information-cultural threats, information-religious threats, information-psychological threats, secularism, interethnic harmony, information inequality, information crime, patriotism, dedication, loyalty, social responsibility.

It is necessary to develop patriotism, self-sacrifice, loyalty, social responsibility in the society as a characteristic of social solidarity. The feeling of homeland creates a strong and reliable immunity in a person against foreign ideas and currents that are contrary to the interests of the homeland. For this, it is necessary for a person to consider justice as a rule in society. Because "justice is living in accordance with the laws, and the law requires everyone to live with virtues, the person who acts justly according to the laws is the most virtuous person. Justice is the best virtue"[1]. Philosopher and scientist E. Yusupov said about the ideological foundations of patriotism: "Patriotism is formed and developed on the basis of certain national culture, ideology, and beliefs." In this sense, the current ideology of national independence forms the theoretical basis of the patriotism of independent Uzbekistan. Patriotism formed on the basis of this ideology is formed and preserved as a national virtue [2]". However, the ideology of national independence could not unite the society and help to form patriotism. That's why this ideology was built on lofty slogans and could not be reflected in practice in life. As a result, it turned into an ideological influence tool consisting of just old sayings.

Today, in the environment of global competition, in the conditions of tense inter-ethnic relations, the need for an ideology in line with the spirit of the times is increasing in the societies. As long as humanity and states exist, the struggle of interests will not end. For this, it is required to "ensure consistent implementation of the concept of state policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of international relations" [3]. On a global scale, most of human history has been marked by socio-economic, political conflicts, riots, various disagreements and wars. Of course, the separate states were able to strengthen their borders and unite the people under certain ideas based on the dreams and thoughts of the people. In the countries that unite their people under one idea and lead their national statehood, it is clearly visible that for many years peace, cooperation, and development by uniting the will of the whole people is visible. For example, countries such as the United States of America, Japan, and China have reached their current level of development under a single flag within their ideologies.

On the contrary, human history has repeatedly witnessed the rise of destructive ideas to the level of a national idea. For example, the ideologies of fascism, nationalism, racism, and

chauvinism, which are historically closer and familiar to us, have appeared as ideologies that serve destruction. In the second half of the 20th century, when the "cold war" was raging between the two political poles that formed in the world, A. Dulles, one of the politicians of the American bloc, put forward the following plan to destroy the opposing side: replace them with false values and force them to believe in these false values. How? We will find like-minded people, helpers and allies in Russia itself. The tragedy of the destruction of the most unruly people on earth, a tragedy of its own scale, the sudden and irreversible extinction of self-awareness, is played out scene by scene. For example, from literature and art, we gradually destroy its social essence. We deprive artists of the pleasure of depicting and researching the processes taking place in the depths of the masses. Literature, theater, cinema - all these describe and develop the lowest human feelings. We fully support and exalt creators who forcefully instill sexuality, violence, betrayal, in a word, all kinds of immorality into the human mind... Honesty and integrity will be laughed at and will not be needed by anyone, will become a thing of the past, a- Insolence and arrogance, lies and deception, drunkenness and drug addiction, fear of animals and greed, betrayal, nationalism and hostility between peoples, and above all, hatred of the Russian people - we spread all this without realizing it. Few, very few people understand or guess what is going on. However, we make such people helpless and ridiculed. We will find ways to discredit them and declare them to be outcasts of society" [4]. Such global changes are causing the formation of national unity before each country and the need for the concept of ideological unity in this process.

Researcher I. Akhmedov in his work entitled "National idea and educational issues in the conditions of globalization" explains how social solidarity is an important phenomenon for societies as follows: "Now there are no remote countries or isolated corners of the world. All regions are becoming components of the world economy and a single information space. The concept of a borderless world, where territories and distances lose their original meaning, is taking shape. Researchers are talking about "global village", "networked society". To describe a qualitatively new level of the speed of this process, a new term is used - the term "hyper globalization" [5], which reflects the increasing speed of international relations in all areas, such as: economy, information, finance, people, goods, money, movement of ideas. will do." Therefore, there is a growing need for ideological understanding, not disunity, for nations in the situation of being swallowed up by powerful cultures in the global arena.

Also, the revolutions and civil wars in the Arab region show that ideological unity and national unity are important events for societies. These revolutions became widely known as the Arab Spring. "Arab Spring" is the figurative name of the wave of revolutionary demonstrations and protests that began on December 18, 2010 in Arab countries. These revolutions took place in Tunisia, Libya, Egypt, Yemen, Bahrain, Syria, Lebanon and other countries. There are many opinions and views about the causes of these events, and everyone measures them with their own judgment. However, it can be witnessed that the failure to ensure social justice in the administration, the failure to unite around a single idea, causes chaos in societies.

At the new stage of development of Uzbekistan, on the threshold of the third renaissance, the need for social solidarity is emphasized by the threats, economic contradictions, inter-ethnic conflicts in the international arena, views related to fragmentation, partiality, tyranny, fragmentation and separatism arising in the context of the conflict between freedom and democratic values and the national and religious values of societies. and actions show. Martin

van Creveld, a strategist, military historian, professor of the University of Jerusalem, said, "By the 21st century, the description of conflicts has changed. Interstate armed conflicts have decreased in the world. However, internal conflicts related to people's spirituality, culture, and ideology have increased sharply, he writes. This worrying thought is not without reason. Because every disturbance in the world, in the country, in the family begins with destructive ideas introduced from outside into the minds of citizens. This, in turn, is a manifestation of far-sighted policy, or in short - "EDOS in disguise", which is implemented under the guise of "Advancement of Freedom and Democracy". Its manifestations are called "controlled chaos", "color revolution", "information war", "psychological war", "Trojan horse", "intellectual field of war", "memplex", "soft power" technologies. Therefore, in this situation, the only correct way is to develop the concept of ideological unity based on real goals and to form a moral unity and solidarity in the society.

Also, the internal stability of the states determines its activity in international relations. The internal stability of the state depends on the level of well-being of the population, along with fair governance and the rule of law. The lack of social justice and other problems related to material needs cause instability and chaos in the states. In such conditions, only the people who believe in the fair policy of the government, the real transience of difficulties, and the patriotism of the management representatives can maintain stability. Conflicts between the people and the government, mistrust, corrupt relations and other factors are the cause of revolutions and confrontations in many countries. As a result, conflicts in society, radical movements, aggressive attitudes and finally acts based on terror arise. In such situations, the importance of ideological unity is also shown. But terrorism can never be compared to freedom movement. Freedom movement appears only in conditions of gross injustice, violation of human rights, increased oppression. And terrorism occurs both where there is justice and where there is not. Terrorism is one of the main means of the spread of transnational criminal structures supported by some corrupt government officials and networks. The 82 goals of the development strategy are aimed at "improving preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing factors that cause extremism and terrorism, improving the socio-spiritual environment, preventing the influence of foreign ideas and solving their problems through systematic work with those who are influenced by them" [6]. In the direction of global terrorism, the results of British scientists' research on "Global transformation" became known to the world community. It says: "There are terrorist and criminal organizations in the world. Despite the passage of hundreds of years, the struggle of these gangs with the state authorities is not over, on the contrary, the scope of the struggle is expanding. Experts estimate that the annual illegal trade turnover of these criminal organizations is 300 billion. exceeded the dollar,"[7] it is said. That is why the ideas of terrorism, religious extremism, and religious fanaticism are working without borders today. It does not exclude even the young countries that have just escaped from the yoke of colonialism and are establishing their new states, the world's strongest countries, the United States of America, England, France, Germany, Russia and other countries. Terrorism also increases with the weakness of ideological unity in the society and the breakdown of national unity. That's why today the internal stability of each country, national unity, ideological unity of the population is considered an important aspect of protection from internal and external threats. Because, "to be honest, I stay up at night thinking about how many young people are wasting their lives today by falling for fake deceptions. Tell yourselves, dear brothers, shouldn't this

bitter truth be stabbed into our hearts? After all, only yesterday these young people were our black-eyed people, our neighbor, our son, our daughter or our niece! When did they go astray, when did they go astray? Why are we oblivious? When and where did we make a mistake? When did our children fall into the hands of strangers? Why did they become enemies of their parents and their country? If we don't prevent this terrible calamity today, if we don't mobilize all our energy, it will be too late tomorrow. public representatives should not stay away from this issue of life and death. You yourself see what is happening in countries like Afghanistan, Syria, Iraq, and Libya? What other examples do you need? Aren't these tragedies necessary for all of us to open our eyes? If we don't give our children a proper upbringing, if we don't stay aware of their behavior and mood every day, every minute, if we don't teach them science and technology, if we don't find a decent job, it is out of the question that we will lose this deposit" [8]. Therefore, uniting young people around one idea, forming responsibility for the fate of the country in them and thereby increasing their social activity ensures social stability in the society.

Also, the necessity of social solidarity in the society in which the foundation of the Renaissance is being laid today is shown by the tasks of opposing the new values that aim to cause instability under the name of "mass culture" in the conditions of the clash of cultures. "Mass culture" gradually changes the structure of a nation's characteristics, values, dress, living, behavior culture, nutrition, satisfaction of needs and other human needs, thereby creating social chaos, chaos and instability. Also, individualism, egoism, egocentrism (lat. ego - me, centrums - center), pessimism (lat. pessimus - very bad, looking at life with a bad eye), nihilism (lat. There are ideas and currents such as nihil, denial, dogmatism, escapism, and nationalism. These currents threaten social unity in the society, exacerbate internal contradictions, promote different ideas and devalue the values of the nation. Therefore, a strong concept of ideological unity is needed in the new stage of development of the society. Because in the state's relations with the world community, in its foreign policy as an open country, there are conditions for various ideological influences. In this regard, the state policy was clearly defined in the speech of the leader of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on the topic "Ensuring social stability, preserving the purity of our holy religion - the need of the times" held on June 15, 2017. After all, if we take into account the increasing danger of religious extremism, terrorism, drug addiction, human trafficking, illegal migration, and "mass culture" around us, the deep meaning and importance of these words will become even more obvious.

At what stages this process will be carried out in Uzbekistan, it is necessary to ideologically connect with the idea of a new renaissance. Based on the requirement of scientific, scientific and technological supply, all links of the field of education should be continuously reformed. The previous two Renaissances took place on a strong spiritual and ideological basis, primarily on the basis of high morality, justice, thirst for knowledge and tolerance. Islam prioritizes honesty and correctness, honesty and justice, knowledge and practical activity above all else.

In conclusion, at the new stage of development of society, social solidarity is a unique national ideology, which is expressed in certain opinions, rules, and thoughts. Its achievement depends on the objective conditions as a set of scientific, technological, economic, social determinants and subjective factors, the provision of social justice in society, social responsibility and social activity of citizens, and the ethical principles and legal norms regulating social relations. National ideological unification serves to activate the qualities of

patriotism, hard work, willpower, conscientiousness, activity, responsibility, patience, kindness, resistance to evil in the hearts of society members.

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